

Aquasomics

Research plan

Version 1.1
2021-Dec-20

Intro

Our main objective is to develop and apply high-throughput analytical strategies to assess environmental and human exposure to emerging contaminants

The main tools that we will develop in the framework of *Aquasomics* are:

- a. Validated target and reliable nontarget methods of analysis of emerging contaminants in surface waters and biofluids
- b. Millifluidic devices to run innovative sample treatments and bioassays

These tools, among many others, will be applied in a large variety of cases to:

- a. Assess the effects of identified CECs in waters and strategies for mitigation.
- b. Estimate the bioaccessible and bioavailable fractions of CECs
- c. Support millifluidic devices to run innovative *in-vitro* bioassays
- d. Study the relationships between certain diseases with the exposure to CECs
- e. Assess the exposure to CECs through urine analysis and wastewater-based epidemiology

Research methodology

The main strategy to study the external and the internal doses is the **(bio)monitoring** of target chemicals in biofluids and tissues and in the environment. The combined application of target and nontarget analysis (NTA) in human biofluids, organisms' tissues and in water samples will allow us to tackle those biomonitoring requirements. In addition to this, it is necessary to understand the way the contaminants can reach to the vascular system. In this sense, bioaccessibility and bioavailability concepts must become reliable and measurable.

Working schedule

WP1. Coordination & Management

Fix the data management plan & research plan

WP2. High throughput analytical procedures

Fine-tune the target methods & annotation pipelines in NTS

WP3. Environmental Health Assessment

Monitoring of CECs in coastal environments and dispersal models of MPs

Optimization of DWTP

Oral bioaccessibility & in vitro bioavailability

WP4 Human biomonitoring

Toxicity of CECs onto human leukocyte populations

PFAS in children plasma

Breast milk & Urine & exposure to xenobiotics

Exposure and CAKUT

Wastewater based epidemiology

WP	Task	Research groups			1Y				2Y			
		EHU	USC	UIB	1Q	2Q	3Q	4Q	5Q	6Q	7Q	8Q
1	1.1	NEL, OZZ	JBQ, RRR, NC	MM	█		█		█		█	
	1.2	MOZ, APS	JL, JC	MR				█				█
	1.3	MOA, AUE	ER, PD	MR		█				█		
	1.4	OGM, EAI	JBQ, JC	MM, MR			█				█	
2	2.1	OZZ, APS, MOZ, BGG, NEL, OZZ, OGM, EAI,	RRR; JBQ, JL, VC, AE, PD,		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	2.2		JBQ, JL									
	2.3			MM, J.LI, DJC, EC, BH, MR, MM, EC, PK, HS	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█
	2.4	APS, LMT	RRR, PD									
3	3.1		JBQ, RRR, VC, ER, MSm, NC,									
	3.2		PM	DL, MM								
	3.3	MOA, AUE, APS, LMT, NEL, JBQ, PD		MS, HS, MM, MM, JGM, J.LI, XC, AS, C, MM, ST, C, EC, MS, HS, DJC, ASU, MF, JT, ST								
	3.4	NEL, MID										
	3.5											
	3.6		PD, JBQ									
	3.7	MOZ, BGG, MID		JBQ								
4	4.1			CM, MR, ASU, MM, EC, VV, CB								
	4.2	NEL, MOZ, EAI, OGM, JB										
	4.3	OZZ, APS, EAI, AUE, OGM	RRR, JBQ, AE, PD									
	4.4	OZZ, APS, MOZ, NEL, APS, AUE,										
	4.5	OZZ, AEI, JB	RRR, JL									
	4.6		JBQ, RRR, AE, PD									

Project Coordination

Tasks

- Draft with the own and common activities for the first year
- Design a calendar for face-to-face and virtual meetings
- Mobility of researchers
- Foster the ties with other research groups
- Outreach and open science

Goals

- Increase the efficiency of the common aims and the cooperative work. Wishful thinking!
- Improve the sense of togetherness
- Increase our coordination weakness
- Upgrade to EU calls
- Increase our visibility

Data Management

Each partner has already developed its own data management plan following common and shared guidelines. These plans are available at this Zenodo site and in the project web site.

https://zenodo.org/communities/aquasomic_project/?page=1&size=20

Research plan

The main common tasks are the following:

- Develop of the research plan (this document) and the data management plan (WP1-task 1.1).
- In the kick-off meeting we have decided to meet virtual every 4 months and to plan a face-to-face meeting for the next summer (WP1)

EHU

The main on -going tasks and activities planned in the short term are the following:

1. Target method for the analysis of xenobiotics in water, urine and plasma samples (WP2-task 2.1)
 - Cosmetics, pesticides, plasticisers and other xenobiotics (PhD projects: Mikel Musatadi¹ & Inés Baciero²)
 - LC-MS/MS and UHPLC-q-Orbitrap method for perfluorinated compounds (PFAS) (PhD project: Anne San Roman³)
 - GC-qTOF analysis of nonpolar xenobiotics (PhD project Inés Baciero)
 - Antibiotic residues (PhD project Irantzu Vergara⁴)
2. Enhanced pipelines for nontarget analysis (WP2-task2.2)
 - Adapted workflows to Compound Discoverer 3.3 (on-going)
 - Use of BioTransformer tool for the identification of metabolites (PhD project Iker Alvarez⁵)
3. Activities related to environmental health assessment (WP3)

¹Basque Government PhD fellowship (UPV/EHU, Jan21)

² Basque Government PhD fellowship (UPV/EHU, Jan22)

³ Basque Government PhD fellowship (Public Health Dept. & UPV/EHU, Jan22)

⁴ UPV/EHU PhD fellowship (Jan 21, PhD project not directly related with this project, but closely linked)

⁵UPV/EHU & UPPA Cotutelle PhD fellowship (Jan 21)

- Monitoring of drinking water treating plants (DWTP) and hospital effluents and wastewater treatment plants (WWTP) (PhD projects: Naroa Lopez-Herguedas⁶ & Iker Alvarez)
 - Optimization of advance oxidation process in a drinking water pilot plant (WP3-task 3.3)
4. Activities related to human biomonitoring (WP4)
- Analysis of PFAS in children plasma samples is planned to be tackled in the first term of 2022 (task 4.2)
 - We have established the framework to work on the CAKUT disease (Biocruces) and in this sense, we have already contacted to a gynecologist, and we have some standard questionnaires to collect the metadata (lifestyle, nourishment...) of the pregnant mothers. (task 4.4)
 - Analysis of endocrine disrupting compounds in children with endocrine disorders (Biocruces)
 - A general agreement with the Basque Biobank is foreseeing to allow the analysis of breast milk samples (task 4.5)

USC / INTECMAR

The main on-going tasks and activities planned in the short term are the following:

1. Improvement of sample preparation procedures for persistent mobile chemicals determination (WP2-task 2.1)
 - In water samples (USC, PhD project: Sandra Mendez)
 - In urine (USC, PhD project: Sandra Mendez)
2. Development of target methods (WP2-task 2.1):
 - Metabolites of plastic additives (bisphenols) in wastewater (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
 - Plastic additives (bisphenols) in urine (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
 - Plastic additives (phthalates and bisphenols) in bivalve samples (INTECMAR)
 - Perfluorinated chemicals in drinking water (USC, PhD project: Javier Lopez)
 - Metabolites of phytocannabinoids in wastewater (USC)
3. Development of nontarget methods (WP2-task2.1):
 - For environmental samples by gas chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry (USC, PhD project: Verónica Castro)
 - For urine (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)

4. Occurrence, fate, and risk of emerging pollutants in aquatic ecosystems (WP3-task 3.1)
 - Screening in water samples in collaboration with NORWATER project (USC)
 - Target analysis of water samples in collaboration with NORWATER project (USC)
 - Screening in mollusk and fish samples collected in Portugal in collaboration with CIIMAR (USC)
 - Target analysis of bivalve mollusks: Plastic additives (phthalates and bisphenols) (INTECMAR)
 - Embryo bioassays of zebrafish *Danio rerio*: Metformin and Simvastatin (CIIMAR in collaboration with USC)
5. Developed of 3D dispersal models of microfibers and microplastics in Galician coastal waters (WP3-task 3.2) (INTECMAR, in collaboration with UIB)
6. Monitoring of exposure to pollutants via urine analysis (WP4-task 4.3)
 - Nontarget analysis (USC)
 - Determination of plastic additives (bisphenols) (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
 - Research stage for ca. 3 months with Dr. Covaci (U. Antwerp) working on in-vitro metabolism studies (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
7. Human exposure assessment through Wastewater-based epidemiology (WBE) (WP4-task 4.6)
 - Amphetamine-like stimulants (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
 - Plastic additives (bisphenols) (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
 - Comparison of the results obtained of bisphenols exposure by WBE with those for urine analysis (USC, PhD project: Andrea Estevez)
 - Phytocannabinoids (USC)

UIB

The main on-going tasks and activities planned within the first two years are the following:

1. Development of 3D printed platforms for miniaturized bioassays (WP2-task 2.3)
 - Application to biomimetic chromatographic columns: Use of covalently attached mAb for diclofenac in influent wastewaters (E.J. Carrasco, postdoc)
2. Novel sorptive composite materials based on 3D printing (WP2-task 2.4)
 - On-line monolithic SPE materials for short-chain PFAs and BPs (MOF-MIP) (E.J. Carrasco, postdoc)
 - On-line electromembrane extraction for salt clean-up and preconcentration of organics (E.J. Carrasco & P.Kuban, Guest UIB)
3. Oral bioaccessibility/toxicity testing of additives from microplastics (MPs) and food-borne MPs (WP3-task 3.4)

- Human/environmental risk assessment using human body fluids and vertebrate/invertebrate sealife fluids (UIB in collaboration with USC, PhD project: Javier López)
 - Investigation of reactive oxygen generation from MPs using on-line chemiluminescence system (FPI PhD student)
4. In-vitro bioavailability tests of organic species associated to microplastics using lipid nanovesicles (WP3-task 3.5)
 - Use of fluorescence membrane probes, NMR sensing and molecular dynamics for estimation of oral absorption properties (Miquel Oliver, postdoc)
 - SPE materials with immobilized liposomes for bioavailability testing of emerging contaminants and drugs (Maria Pau Garcia, PhD project)
 5. In-vivo bioavailability tests and advanced biochemical assays for microplastic additives using murine models (WP3-task 3.6)
 - Acute bioavailability of plasticizers (BPA, DNOP) from ingested MPs in mice blood (Dr. Josep Mercader and Dr. Silvia Tejada, Biochemistry Dep, UIB)
 6. Miniaturized 3D printed fluidic platforms for in-vitro cytotoxicity and ecotoxicity testing (WP3-task 3.7)
 - Use of genetically modified cells with luciferase to monitor effects on nuclear receptors (Dr. Hana Sklenarova, Charles University)
 7. Toxicity of emerging contaminants onto human leukocyte populations using a 3D printed blood vessel (WP4-task 4.1)
 - Development of a static method to investigate interaction of monocytes incubated with contaminants with HUVEC cells (Human endothelial cells) to elucidate inflammatory events (FISABIO lab)